

OPENING LECTURE

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The Symbiotic City

The 21st century Future City will perhaps become the metabolic and symbiotic city?

When the CIAM collapsed in 1958, my feelings were conflicted. I felt anxious regarding the loss of the text the Modern architecture movement, but I was also greatly anticipating what was to come after in architecture and city planning. Seeing these changes, I wrote an essay entitled "From the Age of Machine Principle to the Age of Life Principle" in 1959.

The Metabolism group we formed in 1960 introduced the Metabolism-Recycle concept, which is the key concept of the Age of Life Principle.

The period from the end of the 19th century to the collapse of the CIAM in the middle of the 20th can be defined as the peak of the Modern era. I believe the spirit of this era can be expressed by the phrase "the Age of Machine Principle", particularly when cultural figures such as Le Corbusier called the house a "machine for living", Russian film-director Sergei Eisenstein called cinema a machine, and Italian Futurist Marinetti called the poem a machine.

The Age of Machine Principle gave high esteem to efficiency, dualistic rationalism, productivity, universality, homogeneity, linear hierarchy, and global standardization.

Furthermore, it was the time that elevated the fields of science, technology, and economics, striving to become an industrialized society. Supporting the age of the machine principle were the concepts of Aristotelian and Cartesian dualistic rationalism, Logocentrism, humanism, and Eurocentrism. The "international style" of architecture from the Age of Machine Principle imported the ideas of industrialization and standardization as it spread throughout the world, blind to the existing cultures, traditions, and climates. It was an age that ruled by one exclusive model. The city of the Age of Machine Principle embodied the Athens Charter of the Modern City, the design also following a single model. The ideal city was planned as a final completion; the 'master plan.'

Looking back at history, we know that a city is not defined by the plan from which it originated, but continues to grow and change and develop outside of any boundaries a 'master' plan may have drawn. I think it can be said that a single ideal model of architecture and urban planning does not exist. I contend that there are a variety of models to follow, and that architecture and urban planning should reflect the environment and culture that it inhabits.

Having set forth the hypothesis in my "From the Age of Machine Principle to the Age of Life Principle" in 1959, I truly believe that after 40 years my prediction has come true.

The life principle regards metabolism, recycling, information, ecology, sustainability, symbiosis, and the gene as its important key concepts. From the time I announced my prediction with my essay in 1959, I have based my architecture and urban designs along those concepts.

As part of the Metabolism movement that emerged in 1960, we introduced time as an element of architecture and city design. The design of the building was not restricted to the plan we drew, rather it allowed for the inevitable changes that the future would bring.

The Agricultural City Project (1960) is a metabolic city capable of growth and development. It exists without a center, the elevated pathways forming the megastructure of the agricultural city. Building the city above the rice paddy fields expresses the symbiosis between the urban and the rural, city and agriculture.

The Helix City 1961 is a man-made, 600m-tall spiral megastructure. Houses can be freely built on this man-made structure. The Helix City describes the text of the DNA double-helix structure announced in 1954 by Watson. The gene is the symbol of the Age of Life Principle. Designed to be built on a lake or sea, the Helix City realizes the symbiosis between nature and city. Furthermore it can grow upwards and sideways, making it a model of a metabolic city.

Defined by the lake in the center, the island is a Ring City, the prototype for the 21st century.

The Nakagin Capsule Tower (1972) can accommodate the individual as either a study space or a small sleeping space. The stairs and elevator are contained in the core column, sustaining as the vertical megastructure. The capsules are installed with 2 high-tension bolts, the wiring and ductwork all running exposed along the core column. The capsule's wiring, piping, plumbing, and fixtures can all be easily exchanged and recycled, giving the Nakagin Capsule Tower a long life span as an architectural expression of the concepts metabolism and recycling.

Capsule House K uses the same capsule as the Nakagin Capsule Tower. However, cor-ten (atmo-

spheric corrosion resistant steel) is used for the exterior walls. To preserve the nature of the surrounding steep terrain, the core column is the only part of the architecture that makes contact with the earth. The capsule is mounted on the core column in a cantilever structure. The capsule is composed of a kitchen capsule, two bedroom capsules, and a tea-room capsule.

Fig. 1 - Helix City Plan

The Sony Tower in Osaka (1976) is the vertically standing showroom for Sony Electronics. The elevator, escalator, and toilet are all capsulated, ensuring easy exchange and recycling in the future.

Metabolic architecture and the metabolic city are symbiosis between time—the past, present, and future. Under the ideas of life cycle and recycling, we researched how to construct an architecture that was a sustainable megastructure complete with fixtures that could easily be replaced. Recycling system is another theme of metabolic architecture and the metabolic city. In my theory on urban planning I proposed the idea of planning the city on the metabolic cycle. This idea is close to Louis Kahn's idea of Master Space and Servant Space.

The Life Cycle is divided into long-term naturally existing megastructures—forests, rivers, and man-made megastructure—artificial land, and also into the constantly changing Mechanical System—the wiring, piping for water and sewage, etc. It is through this recycling system that the life of architecture and the city can be extended longer.

In 1971 I named the city of the Age of Life Principle the Eco-City when I had the discussion with economist Professor Kenneth Bolding based on his idea of Eco-systems. In this Eco-City numerous Eco-

Technologies came about. For example, garbage piled up in neglected heaps during the Age of Machine Principle, but the Age of Life Principle City employs garbage as a valuable source for energy and recyclable resources. Through permeable pavement, rainwater can be easily recycled back into the earth. The city that adapts and develops these Eco-technologies is a sustainable city. The design of the city is not only to draw up a terminal master plan, but to organize a master system of structure.

The Age of Life Principle is not based on homogeneity or universality, but on diversity and symbiosis. Culture and the arts should be regarded with the same importance as science, technology, and economics, and thus the Age of Life Principle endeavors to be an age of the information society.

The ideas supporting the Age of Life Principle should change the former notions of Logocentrism and dualistic rationalism to Ecology, sensitivity, and the philosophy of symbiosis.

The belief that man, next to God and holding onto the tenet of reason, is given free reign over all living things is outdated. We now understand that humans are not king of, but *part* of this intricate and expansive ecosystem. Human existence is dependent on the existence of the natural surroundings. The philosophy of symbiosis developed beyond the dualism between city and nature, between man and nature. The city is for humans, but a place to support all sorts of living things, a place to live symbiotically.

The philosophy of symbiosis traverses the dualism between man and nature, between nature and other living things. Therefore, the symbiosis between cutting-edge technology and nature, between multimedia technology and the genetic engineering or biotechnology of living things plays a very important role. Bioelectronics may become the largest industry of the 21st century. If that is so, then we can expect agriculture, biotechnology, and multimedia technology to be in symbiosis as the 21st century's advanced industry. For this up-coming era, the Eco-City has already been progressing, to the Eco-media City I gave name to long ago.

The 21st century's largest growing industries will be the multimedia industry, the logistics industry, and the ecological industry. Further into the future the union of these three industries, Eco-Media and Bio-Electronics industries will be the dominating industries.

In Japan alone, the market size of these three industries is speculated to become 420 trillion yen, 140 trillion-yen per industry, from the year 2010 to 2015. This will of course have an impact on the future's cities, cities that I call Eco-media Cities.

The three infrastructure systems important to the Eco-media City are: optic fiber and wireless com-

munications, the so-called information super highway are infrastructure for the multi-media industry; airports, harbors, highways, railways, and related facilities are infrastructure for the logistics industry; nature which contains genetic resources and Eco-corridors are infrastructure for the Eco-industry.

All these infrastructure must be combined for the future city.

A new highway system needs to be constructed to link the airports, sea ports, harbors, and cargo railway stations.

Ten years ago at the environmental summit in Brazil, a treaty was signed to promote the diversification of living species, or bio-diversity. The purpose was to prevent the extinction of the earth's valuable species of plants and animals, and thereby protect global bio-diversity. From the point of view of Darwin's theory of natural selection, the disappearance of valuable forms of life is a natural consequence of evolution. The Brazil summit indeed announced the inauguration of an Age of Symbiosis with its rejection of the virtually supremacist way of thinking and its assertion that the proper way towards evolution is in the symbiosis of diverse species.

According to current research, worldwide urbanization and the destruction of forests for agricultural purposes, etc., have severed Eco-Systems everywhere, interfering with the species passing back and forth between different Eco-System areas. The creation of linear forests and ecological corridors to form networks among isolated areas of Eco-Systems makes it possible for insects, butterflies, birds, small animals and other living species to move back and forth through large areas. The resulting interaction and symbiosis of various species of life is the most effective means of maintaining bio-diversity. Recent experiments have demonstrated that a corridor of forest as little as 20 meters wide is sufficient to support the movement of diverse species.

The importance of the Eco-corridor lies in its strategic value as a means of preserving bio-diversity, but there are two further implications to this, as well.

One is that our concern for diversification of species is implicit within a new vision of symbiosis among differing cultures which would encompass the wish to preserve all of the world's diversified and mutually distinctive cultures and to encourage cultural pluralism.

A second is that the three infrastructures of the Eco-Media City—interactive worldwide networks such as the Internet, borderless logistics, and Eco-corridors for promoting bio-diversity—are all infrastructures of the Future City for the Age of Symbiosis which will follow modernism and industrial society.

Symbiosis between nature and architecture

The symbiosis between nature and architecture can be realized through the intermediate zone, the man-made landscape (roof garden) that joins the

wild, existing nature and constructions like architecture and cities.

The architecture follows along the contour line or undulation of the land as symbiosis between the architecture and nature is realized through the landscaping and plantation of the rooftops.

In the design for the Public Space System along the Central axis of Shenzhen, (1997-) next to Hong Kong, I proposed the new city center of Eco-Media City. The axis of the city is 300 hectares, with a width ranging from 350m to 700 m, including Lian Hua Mountain, which is equal in size to Central Park in New York City. This axis contains one and two-story buildings (one floor above and one floor below the ground). It is also quite possible to create an ecological corridor with the roof as man-made ground for an experimental park.

Fig. 2 - Shenzhen

The Eco-media City will be an experimental city for the symbiosis of man-made nature and cities; Eco-systems and electronics and human beings and other life.

The man-made nature created on the roof of the huge one or two-story building will become an urban ecological corridor connecting man-made forests and the Lian Hua Mountains and extend to Shenzhen Bay.

Nature is important not only as landscape, but also as the shelter for the genes existing on the earth. Genes will be strategic resources of the 21st Century. The leading industry the 21st Century will be the symbiosis of genetic engineering and electronics (multi-media), the so-called bioelectronics.

This huge low rise city center contains a city hall, an information center, a business support center (incubation center), a convention center, an art center, an art gallery, a recycling center, an energy center, a distribution center, a shopping center, a parking lot among other facilities.

60 km south of Kuala Lumpur, the initial stage of the New Kuala Lumpur International Airport has been completed. 2 highways, a high-speed railway,

fiber optics and other infrastructure will be constructed between Kuala Lumpur and the airport. Two Eco-Corridors are planned between the existing city Kuala Lumpur and the new airport.

Fig. 3 - Kuala Lumpur

Except for a few hilly sections, this land is flat and measures 10 kilometers by 10 kilometers, or 100 square kilometers.

After selected as an architect, by International Nominated Competition, I suggested to the Malaysian government that they should formulate a regional development plan before random development overruns the area between Kuala Lumpur City and the new airport. This was the Eco-Media City concept, a KL Linear Capital Corridor Concept.

My proposal called for the creation of a completely new experimental city for the 21st century by building logistics, information, and ecological infrastructures in the area between Kuala Lumpur City and the new airport.

Later, the Multimedia Super Corridor (MSC) plan was formulated as the plan for the information infrastructure. An intelligent city (IT)—the Cyber Jaja—is developed as a Silicon Valley-type area as part of the new capital plan.

The new capital plan was put forward as a plan to move the government offices to a location midway between Kuala Lumpur City and the new capital. The Prime Minister's residence and other structures have already been completed at the same time as the new airport.

The ecological corridor is still in the planning stage. This will gradually take shape for the future.

Creating a forest surrounding the airport would be the most effective method for blocking the airport noise. This is the basis of the concept for the symbiosis between forest and airport. In addition, we also think this would be effective for expressing the identity of the Malaysian topography.

The symbiosis between forest and airport involves more than a forest planned for airport's exterior. In addition, a miniature tropical rain forest will be created inside the airport between the main terminal building and the contact pier, and in the inner court in the center of the satellite building. It means Forest in Airport, Airport in Forest.

Both the people arriving at and departing from KLIA will come into contact with this forest, providing them with a sense of the Malaysian identity.

The completion of the current Phase I of KLIA will result in two 4,000 meter runways and a 334,300 square meter main terminal building. Phase I will enable the handling of 25 million passengers a year. Ultimately, however, the airport will be able to handle 120 million passengers annually by 2020.

The metabolic system was emphasized for this ambitious plan for an international hub airport. The idea for this airport to be comprised of cell units of Hyperbolic Paraboloid shells (H-P shells) with large spans of 38.4 meters was planned through the program for future expansion.

The concept of a structure with a conical shape and an H-P shell would be the best way to express to the greatest extent possible the identity of the Malaysian traditional and Islamic culture in abstract form.

The cross-section view of the H-P shell central axis is an arch.

An interior space created by the integration of the H-P shells would connote a continuous Islamic dome. Horizontal thrust would be generated at the base of the H-P shell. Though one method for resolving this would be to place tension wire between column capitals, we decided on a conical column made by cantilever column from the base.

The city of the Age of the Machine Principle was separated into functions—giving rise to the commercial, residential, industrial, and recreational areas. But, the city of the 21st century will be a symbiosis of different functions with more complicated and integrated combinations.

The symbiotic city also demands symbiosis between the generations. From babies to teenagers, and onto the elderly, they all need to communicate and interact. It is such a symbiotic city that will be the city of the 21st century, the city of the Age of the Life Principle.

This 21st century city also demands symbiosis between the past and the future. As our genes contain

our historical information, the city, too, must also contain historical information.

Information can be inherited from old buildings, old towns. Buildings that have no academic value must be preserved if they tell an important story of history. Hiroshima's A-bomb Dome may not have academic value, but is a tangible reminder of the tragedy that befell the city, and to also serve as a monument vowing to preserve peace.

Transportation of the city of the Age of Machine Principle played an important role as the belt connected the parts. In the Age of Life Principle, in addition to transportation, information further joins people together, and information plays a role of connections between people and spaces. Alvin Toffler proposed the concept of the Electrical Cottage in his book *The Third Wave*. He made the prediction that in the information society, through the computer, people could live anywhere, work anywhere, thus decentralizing the city. I, however, predict that the information society will thrive more on the centralization of cities. One reason being that through the Internet, people will be stimulated to meet with each other, and thus, will need urban spaces for face-to-face communication.

Therefore a high level of attention is devoted to the streets for pedestrians, and also given to the design of an atrium inside the building to allow for direct interaction between people.

Architecture and urban space from the era of Modernism, from the Age of Machine Principle, were split too clearly into the binary of public and private. The life principle city will strive to recognize the intermediary area between the public and the private spaces, the common space. Long ago internalized exterior space, for example the portico and galleria that is covered street, played an important role as common space that was neither public nor private. The scale of the shared space meets the scale of the architecture and the city, connecting the groups of architecture and the rows of towns together.

The thought for regarding this intermediary space with importance can also be found in traditional Japanese culture: the *engawa*, or, covered terrace, from the Sho'in and Sukiya styles of architecture was the space between the interior and exterior; the reserved white space in calligraphy; and the intervals of silence, *ma*, in music.

The Age of Machine Principle, a high population density was an evaluated bad condition, and the low-density garden city was idealized. The Age of Life Principle's city will perhaps be compacted and densely populated. This compact city can be high-rise-high-density; mid-rise-high-density; low-rise-high density. The variations of these are of course dependent upon variables such as climate, culture identity, and the surrounding environment.

To talk more about the idea of space for direct interaction and face-to-face communication in the housing area, however, we need low-rise-high-density space that allows for these.

It is believed that the world population will reach 10 billion by the year 2050. If we continue to live in such low-density population areas, urban sprawl along with the forced expansion of farming land will destroy the forests, paving the way for our own extinction. Saving the forests and preserving the variety of natural species in symbiosis with each other is the only way to preserve our own existence into the 21st century.

To provide for that, even each regional towns and country villages must make efforts without exception to live in these compacted, densely populated cities.

These compacted regional cities should create a networking system. The nature and agricultural and landscaped areas between these cities must be preserved in order to protect our eco-systems.

City parks should not be set apart in their own neighborhood, but should be integrated as green linear networks. These green networks are not to provide exclusive safe pathways for humans; they exist to support areas for small animals, insects, and birds to roam and inhabit as ecological corridors.

The Age of Machine Principle was the age of humanism. Things were designed exclusively for humans.

In the Age of Life Principle, the city's parks will be designed as part of an ecological corridor. The Future City of the 21st century is a city of symbiosis, a metabolic city, a recycling city, a sustainable city.

Now I would like to talk about a project I've been working with, the 21st century's first experimental city, the plan for the new capital of Kazakhstan. This new capital, Astana, is a metabolic, symbiotic, and sustainable Eco-city.

I received first prize in the international competition held in 1998, and currently, the planning is being funded by the ODA, of the Japanese government.

Three major characteristics of the new capital Astana are the following: first is Astana will be a symbiotic city. As protection against the strong winter winds, 10,000 ha of forest in the southwest region are planned. Further forest development is carried out through the technique of alternating forest and wheat fields in a banded fashion. To regenerate the ecosystems of Kazakhstan plains, a green network and Eco-Corridor connect the forests with the city parks. This is an experiment to harbor the symbiosis between the new city and the forests.

The center of the new city is set along the Ishim River that flows along the south border of the existing city. The river, as nature, along with the man-made lake that also serves as a balancing pond, is in symbiosis with the city.

The streets of the existing city will also be preserved as much as possible in symbiosis with the new capital, symbiosis of history and the future.

To ensure the symbiosis between the historical and the contemporary, strong efforts are being paid to preserve the streets and historical architecture of the existing city.

Astana will strive to become a city where the different peoples—Kazakhstanians, Russians, Kirgizians, Germans, etc.—and their different cultures exist in symbiosis.

The region will keep the know-how gained from wheat agriculture and latest biotechnology to foster the new agriculture of soybeans and corn as one of the new capital's industries. It will also develop the symbiotic relationship between the city and agriculture, high-tech industry and agriculture.

The second characteristic is that Astana will be a metabolic city. Because the government officials' residences are the first to be relocated, the capital will become a city that grows quickly. To follow the changes and to grow, a flexible master system and master program are employed rather than a fixed master plan.

A linear zoning system that can expand along the east-west axis is also being proposed. Through the 3-ring road system and the cluster ring road system in the housing area, the capital can grow like the cell-city metabolically.

The third characteristic is that Astana will be a sustainable Eco-City. Rainwater is recycled back into the earth through permeable pavement, supplying water to the trees along the roads and forests. Garbage from kitchens will be produced as solid fuel and as fertilizer for agricultural use. The city's sewage and drainage water will be purified and used for the forests and farming. Natural gas power stations will be introduced to replace coal power stations to help reduce carbon dioxide emissions, making a contribution to improve the environment. To make use of the strong winds, a large-scale wind power generation system is also planned.

By the year 2030, the whole picture of metabolic symbiotic Future City of the 21st century will be seen.

Architecture that strives to foster symbiosis between the past and the present cannot simply copy the shapes of architecture as they were—this would be nothing more than creating works like the vulgar toy "historical" buildings of Disneyland.

I propose using the abstract symbolic method, of which there are 2 approaches.

The first approach is to use signs, like the letters of the alphabet, which are then combined to create a word, leading to the combination of words which create literature. When applying this method to architecture, I use geometric shapes, like the cube, the sphere, the cone, the cylinder, the pyramid, the el-

lipse, the triangle, the half-circle, the hemisphere, signs like the alphabet common to everyone. From the time of ancient Egypt and China to the contemporary era, these shapes have been used as letters of architecture's alphabet. By altering the proportions of the geometric shapes, varying the materials, or changing the placement within an identity of cultures and regions and meanings can be expressed.

For example, a splayed cone can represent the Japanese traditional hat of a woman, the hat of a Chinese farmer, or the roof of an Indonesian village.

The towers of European castles are topped with cone-shaped roofs, the titanium noses of jet fighter planes are sharp cones.

The Chinese-Japanese Youth Center was built in 1990 by a grant-in-aid from the ODA of the Japanese government in collaboration with funding from the Chinese government, becoming a symbol of the relationship between China and Japan. This architecture is additionally an example of abstract symbolism.

The hotel, gymnasium, and training facility are rendered in abstract geometric forms like the cylinder, square, rectangle, ellipse, and circle.

One important characteristic is the hotel and auditorium, the sphere resting on a square base. This square-circle element is a symbolic quote of the outlook on the universe from the *tennennchihou* belief, written in *Enanji* in the era of Han dynasty of ancient China, where a circle represented heaven and a square represented the earth.

By escaping a completely symmetric form, the architecture also expresses the Japanese aesthetic of asymmetry.

Through the use of pretextual symbols and traditional aesthetics, the Chinese Youth Culture Center expresses symbiosis between the past and the present abstractly.

Furthermore, symmetrical arrangement of geometric shapes means a classical European aesthetic sense, while an asymmetrical random layout describes the unique Japanese aesthetic.

The second method is using ideogrammatic symbols, like those of Chinese characters. Chinese characters, or *kanji*, are a result of taking the shape of something like a bird or mountain and then abstracting it into a character.

If I copied traditional shapes directly, it is not creative, but once abstracted like a Chinese character then it is a creation.

Architecture must express the spirit of the era from which it was created.

I believe the spirit of the Modern era can be expressed by the word 'abstract'. Abstract painting, sculpture, music, modern architecture that are all examples of abstraction. It is through the abstraction of traditional forms and shapes that we can realize the symbiosis between the past and the present.

I.M. Pei's glass pyramid at the entrance to the Louvre and Danish architect Spretkelsen's Grande Arche in Paris are masterpieces representative of abstracted symbolism.

I believe that abstract symbolism is an important creative method capable of fostering symbiosis between global standardization and local identity, between the past and the present.

Architecture and cities in 21st Century will be created by the philosophy of symbiosis.

KEYWORDS

Metabolism, Recycle, Ecology, Symbiosis, Information.

Kisho Kuroka. Hon. FAIA, Hon. FRIBA, Founder of the Metabolism group (1960). His recent works are the New Wing of the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam, the Kuala Lumpur New International Airport, and the Osaka International Convention Center. He is currently planning the new city center of Shen Zhen¹¹ (pop. 4 million) in China, and the new capital of Kazakhstan in central Asia. He is author of the renowned Philosophy of Symbiosis (Tokyo, Tokuma Publishing Co.)